

PREPARATION AND CHARACTERISATION OF NANOPARTICLE-DOPED COMMINGLED COMPOSITES FOR IMPROVED FIRE PERFORMANCE

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1 Introduction

The use of polymer fibre-reinforced composites has been growing at a remarkable rate over the last decades. This is due to the superior mechanical properties which polymer matrix fibre-reinforced composites exhibit over traditional materials such as metals, superalloys and ceramics.

While these properties have made composite very attractive for the aerospace and marine industry, to name a few, composites pose some drawbacks, which prevent them from fully replacing traditional materials in primary applications. One of these is the poor fire performance, which is mainly attributed to the organic matrices that are utilised in composite materials. In particular, at elevated temperatures these organic resins soften, causing a considerable deterioration of mechanical properties whilst at high temperatures they decompose and produce smoke and toxic or flammable products [1-3]. In addition, these products can also burn and release heat, which can lead to flame spread and fire exacerbation. Finally, depending on the heat flux and the loading conditions, a composite component can collapse in a matter of few minutes which can have a detrimental effect on the overall structural capacity and performance [1-7].

Even though a large number of polymer resins are flammable and thus their respective composites, ways to improve their low inherent fire retardancy using clay fillers have been suggested and studied thoroughly in the literature [8-9]. Initially, fillers in the microscale had been added to polymers to increase the fire performance. However, high filler loadings are generally required to improve the fire retardancy which has significant ramifications to the mechanical properties. This was overcome with the use of nanofillers which not only provided a higher surface area but also required lower quantities to increase the fire retardancy of the base system.

Although the incorporation of nanoclays into the resin has been extensively studied, there is a shortage of studies where continuous fibre reinforcement is also involved. In such cases, issues relating to high viscosity and particle filtration have been reported [1,10].

This study describes the development and fire reaction of novel nanoparticle modified commingled fibre-reinforced composites [11]. In particular, the concept behind this work has been to initially obtain fire-optimised matrix formulations which would then be melt-spun into continuous fibres and eventually commingled with conventional glass fibres to produce composite preforms for consolidation (Fig. 1). During consolidation, the very short polymer flow lengths, which are characteristic of commingled fibre composite systems along with the use of sub-micron-scale particulate fillers that are unlikely to be filtered-out by the fibre reinforcements during processing, would provide an extremely even and efficient distribution of the fire-retarding additive throughout the composite part. Such a novel approach is regarded as a highly efficient means of dispersing fire retarding particles within a fibre-reinforced polymer composite. This fibre-level doping of the polymer, along with the use of commingling for mixing the fibre and resin, should overcome the existing practical difficulties of achieving high particle loadings with conventional composites, namely excessive resin viscosity and undesirable fibre filtration of the particles.

The work presented here is part of a wider ongoing project - "FIRE-RESIST – Developing Novel Fire-Resistant High Performance Composites". FIRE-RESIST aims to develop novel, cost-effective and yet high-performance polymer matrix composites with a step-change improvement in fire behaviour [11].

2 Manufacturing

In this section the process from fibre spinning to manufacturing of commingled fibre-reinforced composite laminates is described.

2.1 Materials

The thermoplastic polymer system which was used in this study was Polyamide 6 or PA6. PA6 is a semicrystalline polyamide used in applications where temperature and chemical resistance are critical and also exhibits good fire-retardancy properties. This material system was supplied by BASF under the commercial name Ultramid® B27 03 having a reported density of 1.12–1.15 cm³/g (ISO 1183) [12]. Regarding the nano-reinforcing clay particles, the clay system which was chosen to increase the fire-retardancy of the neat thermoplastic polymer was Cloisite® 30B or alkyl quaternary ammonium salt bentonite, supplied by Rockwood Additives [13]. Finally, for fibre reinforcement 3B Advantex® glass fibres (200tex) were used [14].

2.2 Fibre Spinning

For the fibre spinning a bi-component melt spinning line with in-line solid state drawing supplied by Extrusion Systems Limited (ESL), UK, was employed (Fig. 2) [15]. Initially, the neat PA6 and PA6+2%wt Cloisite systems, after having been dried at 140°C for 4–6 hours, were fed to Hopper 2 and melted in an 18 mm single screw extruder, while the polymer melt was metered to the spin pack via gear pump. On the melt-spinning line shown in Figure 4, the spinning of the single component PA6 and PA6+2%wt Cloisite fibres was done simply by shutting down the Extruder 1 and the Gear Pump 1. For Extruder 2, the temperatures in the three heating zones were set to be 240°C, 250°C and 260°C, respectively, whilst the temperatures of gear pump and spin pack were both set to be 260°C. The resulting products of the fibre spinning of neat PA6 and PA6+2%wt Cloisite are shown in Fig.4. It should be noted that fibres with 4% wt Cloisite were also drawn; however, it was difficult to obtain continuous fibres because the fibres were very fragile [16].

2.3 Fibre Commingling

Upon obtaining the fibres from the melt-spinning process, fibre commingling followed in order to obtain the preforms which would then be

consolidated. For the fibre commingling, a four-axis Waltritsch & Wachter filament winding machine was utilised.

Initially, the PA6 and PA6+2%wt Cloisite along with 3B Advantex® Glass fibres (200tex) were fed into the filament winding machine. The fibres were then drawn over a steel plate (100×100×3 mm and 260×260×3 mm) acting like a spindle along one direction (nominally 0° direction) for twenty (20) rounds (Fig. 4). Finally, in order to prevent the preform from swelling during consolidation, a few fibres were drawn perpendicular to the 0° direction. The resulting preforms (100×100×3 mm and 260×260×3 mm) from the fibre commingling are shown in Fig. 5.

2.4 Composite Laminate Manufacturing

The preforms obtained by the fibre commingling, described previously, were subsequently taken to an 80-ton Talent mould carrier for consolidation. Initially, the preforms were consolidated at 260°C using 25-ton pressure (Batch 1). While visually the laminates were of good quality, optical microscopy revealed that considerable porosity was present (discussed in Chapter 3). For this reason, a slight adjustment in the temperature and pressure was made, i.e. the consolidation was conducted at 280°C using pressure of 35-ton (Batch 2). This adjustment resulted in improved viscosity and lower porosity (see Chapter 3). The manufactured commingled fibre-reinforced composite laminates are shown in Fig. 6 and Fig. 7. The manufacturing process comprised eight (8) laminates in total, and in particular two laminates of each system (G/PA6 and G/PA6+2%wt Cloisite) from each consolidation scheme (Batch 1 and Batch 2).

3 Experimental

This section provides a description of the experimental procedure which was conducted with the aim to provide information about the microstructure, the thermal properties as well as the fire reaction of the neat and nanoparticle-doped PA6 laminates.

3.1 Microstructure

Prior to investigating the microstructure of the neat PA6 and PA6+2%wt Cloisite commingled composite laminates, ISO 3451 and ASTM D2584 tests were performed to determine the volume fraction of the glass reinforcement. Samples of both

material systems, PA6 and PA6+2%wt Cloisite, were weighed and placed into dried and pre-weighed porcelain crucibles. The porcelain crucibles were then heated in an oven at 565°C in air atmosphere for 5 hours and finally, they were weighed after having cooled down. The nominal densities for the PA6 and glass fibres were 1.130g/cm³ and 2.260g/cm³ respectively.

To investigate the microstructure of the neat PA6 and PA6+2%wt Cloisite commingled composite laminates, optical microscopy was performed on a Nikon Eclipse LV150N optical microscope and images were acquired by a Nikon DS-Fi2 camera. For the microscopic inspection, numerous specimens acquired from G/PA6 and G/PA6+2%wt Cloisite laminates were ground and polished up to 1 µm grit size (diamond suspension) in a Struers Rotopol 1® polishing machine.

3.2 Dynamic Mechanical Analysis

The Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA) is an experimental method in which an oscillating force is applied to a sample and the material's response is analysed. From this method, the tendency to flow (viscosity) and stiffness can be obtained, which are greatly dependent on the applied stress, external temperature and loading time/frequency. In this work DMA (Q800 supplied by TA Instruments) was used to obtain the elastic modulus over a temperature range, i.e. -30°C–200°C. Finally, stress was introduced to the samples (50×10×3 mm) in a 3-point bending fixture at a frequency of 1 Hz (Fig. 8). DMA also provided information regarding the $\tan \delta$, the tangent of the phase angle or damping, which is given by Equation 1:

$$\tan \delta = E'/E'' \quad (1)$$

where E' is the storage modulus (a measure of a material's elastic response) and E'' is the loss modulus (a measure of a material's viscous response).

3.3 Fire reaction tests

3.3.1 Cone Calorimeter

Cone calorimeter (CC) is a bench-scale test which measures fire reaction properties of combustible materials in oxygen environment. This method is versatile and widely used in fire safety and provides a series of fire reaction properties, heat release rate, time-to-ignition, smoke density, and yields of CO₂

and CO, to name a few. Cone calorimetry was conducted for both unreinforced and glass fibre-reinforced PA6 and PA6+2%wt Cloisite laminates, using 100×100×3 mm specimens (three per material system). In the case of the unreinforced laminates, cone calorimetry was conducted at 35 KW/m², whilst for the glass fibre-reinforced laminates fluxes of 35, 50 and 70 KW/m² were used.

3.3.2 UL-94

UL-94 is a small-scale flame test, developed by Underwriters Laboratories Inc. to evaluate the flammability of polymeric materials. In this test, the specimens were exposed to flame and their behaviour was assessed in terms of the "afterflame" time or the amount of material burned in a specific length of time. In particular, 5 specimens of each material system (PA6 and PA6+2%wt Cloisite) with dimensions 125×30×3 mm were tested under vertical flame. In that vertical test flame, the flame was applied to the base of the specimen held in vertical position and upon removal of the flame, the extinguishing time was determined. Prior to testing the specimens were conditioned at 23°C and 50% humidity for at 48 hours, while a methane fuel burner.

4 Results

In the following section, the results from the experimental procedure of the glass fibre-reinforced PA6 and PA6+2%wt Cloisite laminates are reported. Initially, the findings from the fibre volume fraction estimation as well as the observations from the optical microscopy are presented. Subsequently, the change in the storage modulus with increasing temperature (DMA) is shown for the neat and nanoparticle-doped PA6, while finally the results from the fire reaction tests (Cone Calorimetry and UL-94) are reported.

4.1 Microstructure

The calcination (ISO 3451) and resin burn (ASTM D2584) tests showed that the glass fibre volume fraction in the commingled G/PA6 laminate was approximately 54% whilst in the commingled G/PA6+2%wt Cloisite laminate it was approximately 51%. The results from the two tests are tabulated in Table 1.

While the aforementioned tests provided an estimation of the constituents' volume fraction, optical microscopy offered a more thorough image

of the microstructure of the two systems. With regards to the laminates from the first manufacturing round (Batch 1), optical microscopy revealed that in the commingled G/PA6+2%wt Cloisite laminates, the fibres were not well distributed in the matrix and that the void content was higher in contrast to the G/PA6 laminates (Fig. 9 and Fig. 10). In particular, in the G/PA6+2%wt Cloisite laminates, wide resin-rich areas as well as areas where large amount of agglomerated glass fibres were observed. In such areas voids up to eight fibre diameters were evident (Fig. 10). Concerning the G/PA6, in general the glass fibres were well distributed; however, limited areas of glass fibre agglomerations were also observed where voids of not larger than two fibre diameters were evident. Note that the numerous black-coloured speckles throughout the micrographs do not correspond to voids but to the shuttered surfaces of the glass fibres due to grinding and polishing.

The findings from the optical microscopy in the Batch 1 laminates suggested that adjustments in the manufacturing process were necessary in order to improve the wetting and the distribution of the glass fibres within the neat and nanoparticle-doped PA6 matrix. Indeed, the adjustments in the consolidation process, i.e. the increase of temperature and pressure to 280°C and 35-ton respectively, improved both the fibre wetting and distribution and reduced significantly the void content. As Fig. 10 and Fig. 11 illustrate, the improvement of the fibre distribution was large, especially for the G/PA6+2%wt Cloisite laminate where no voids and large glass fibre agglomerates were evident, implying that the flow of the resin and the wetting of the fibres was greatly improved. Nevertheless, large resin-rich areas were still observed in the G/PA6+2%wt Cloisite laminates.

4.2 Dynamic Mechanical Analysis

The results from the Dynamic Mechanical Analysis of the commingled G/PA6 and G/PA6+2%wt Cloisite composite laminates (Batch 1 and Batch 2) are shown in Fig.13. Initially, the representative storage modulus (E') versus temperature curves indicated a large drop of the storage modulus with increasing temperature, as expected. Both systems from Batch 1 exhibited lower storage modulus across the temperature range in comparison to the laminates from Batch 2. With regards to the laminates from Batch 2, both systems exhibited similar curves. While the storage modulus of the

G/PA6 was higher up to 50°C, the G/PA6+2%wt Cloisite system exhibited consistently higher storage modulus from 50°C to 180°C. Moreover, the total drop in the storage modulus (from -30°C to 200°C) was larger in the nanoparticle-doped laminates (up to approximately 80%) compared to the G/PA6 laminates (up to approximately 65%). Finally, DMA also provided information about $\tan \delta$ with increasing temperature for the four laminates. In fact, the onset of the peak in the $\tan \delta$ curve can be taken as the glass transition temperature, T_g . Considering this, it can be said that the G/PA6+2%wt Cloisite laminates from both batches exhibited higher T_g than the G/PA6 laminates (Fig. 13).

4.3 Fire reaction tests

4.3.1 Cone Calorimetry

Prior to assessing the fire reaction of the commingled G/PA6 and G/PA6+2%wt Cloisite composite laminates, Cone Calorimetry was conducted in unreinforced PA6 and PA6+2%wt Cloisite specimens at 50 kW/m² incident heat flux (Fig. 15). Considering the behaviour of the two systems, the incorporation of 2%wt Cloisite significantly decreased the heat release rate compared to the neat PA6 (Table 2). In particular, the drop in the peak heat release rate was approximately 40%, however the change in total released heat and the time-to-ignition were moderate. Finally, in the nanoparticle doped system the smoke production increased by approximately 50%, however the variability was significant in both systems (Table 2). Note that the increase in the content of the Cloisite nanoparticles to 4% had limited effect on the heat release rate.

Regarding the commingled glass fibre-reinforced composite laminates, typical heat release rate (HRR) vs. time curves (35 kW/m²) for the two systems are presented in Fig.16 whilst the results are tabulated in Table 3. In this case the incorporation of the nanoparticles decrease the heat release rate and the time-to-ignition by approximately 15%, while it led to an increase in the total released heat and smoke production by approximately 17% and 40% respectively. It should be noted that the presence of glass fibres apparently reduced heat release rate because flammable matrix fractional volume is decreased in the reinforced composite. At the same time however, time-to-ignition was strongly reduced

from 75 to 47 s (Table 2 and Table 3). Nevertheless, such a decrease in the heat release was also observed in the commingled G/PA6 laminates (Table 2 and Table 3) in comparison to the unreinforced PA6 laminates. Thus, the introduction of the glass fibres had a significant impact in the fire reaction in addition to the presence of the nanoparticles.

Representative heat release rate (HRR) vs. time curves obtained by Cone Calorimetry test at 50 kW/m² are shown in Fig.17 and the results are summarised in Table 4. At 50 kW/m² the improvement in the peak heat release rate was moderate (approximately 10%) while an increase in the time-to-ignition, total released heat and smoke production was observed (Table 4). Note that the behaviour over time did not differ between the two systems. Finally, as for the fire reaction of the two systems at 70 kW/m² heat flux, considering Fig. 18 and Table 5, the doping of the laminates with 2%wt Cloisite did not have any considerable effect in the PHHR, time-to-ignition and smoke production whilst led to a moderate decrease in the total released heat.

4.3.2 UL-94

The results from the open flame UL-94 fire tests are presented in Table 6 and Table 7, for the unreinforced and commingled glass fibre-reinforced PA6 and PA6+2%wt Cloisite composites respectively. With respect to the unreinforced laminates (Table 6), even though a large variation was observed in the total burning time of the PA6 laminates, the total burning time was significantly lower for the PA6/2%wt Cloisite laminates. In fact, the total time was so low because the specimens were self-extinguished and as a result the residual mass was also larger. Ditto, the improvement in the total burning time was significant in the case of the commingled glass fibre-reinforced PA6/2%wt Cloisite in comparison to the G/PA6 (Table 7). Even though the total burning time increased with the introduction of glass-fibres (G/PA6/2%wt Cloisite), the specimens were also self-extinguished and thus the residual mass was larger compared to the G/PA6 laminates.

5 Discussion

In this study, the manufacturing of commingled G/PA6 and G/PA6+2%wt Cloisite composite laminates using melt-spun PA6 and PA6+2%wt Cloisite fibres proved that commingling is an

efficient way to introduce fire-retarded nanoparticles within a composite laminate. Using appropriate temperature and pressure during consolidation (280°C and 35-ton) led to a satisfactory glass fibre volume fraction, wetting and distribution, indicating that the correct manufacturing settings are essential to fully exploit the capabilities of such a process.

While the introduction of 2%wt Cloisite proved to be insufficient to provide any significant improvement in the elastic performance with increasing temperature, the fire reaction tests indicated that it can have a great impact in the fire behaviour of the PA6. In particular, in the unreinforced PA6+2%wt Cloisite laminates the incorporation of the Cloisite nanoparticles led to a significant improvement of the heat release rate (40% – Cone Calorimetry), and the total burning time (UL-94), while it had no effect on the time-to-ignition. This, coupled with the fact that increasing the Cloisite nanoparticle content to 4% did not yield any notable improvement, implies that 2%wt Cloisite nanoparticle content is adequate in order to provide a satisfactory improvement in the fire reaction of the PA6.

Upon commingling and introduction of the glass fibres, some interesting observations were made from the fire reaction tests. Whilst in the Cloisite nanoparticle-doped laminates the heat release rate was further depressed, a significant decrease in the heat release rate was observed in the G/PA6 laminates (compared to the unreinforced laminates), implying that the presence of the glass fibres plays a significant role even without the presence of the fire retardant particles. Even though some hypotheses can be made regarding the behaviour of the glass fibres during fire in the particular system, such as the role of the conductivity of the glass fibres, this phenomenon is not fully understood and therefore further studies are required. Nevertheless, the results presented in this study indicate that introducing fire-retardant nanoparticles using commingling can provide with significant improvements in the fire performance of thermoplastic polymers.

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Fig.1. Schematic of the use of commingled fibres to provide a high performance fire-retarded fibre-reinforced polymer composite part [11].

Fig.2. Schematic of melt-spinning process [15].

Fig.3. Neat PA6 (left) and PA6+2% wt Cloisite fibres.

Fig.4. Filament winding fixture.

Fig.5. Preforms of commingled G/PA6 (top) and G/PA6+2% wt Cloisite fibres (bottom).

Fig.6. Commingled G/PA6 fibre-reinforced composite laminate.

Fig.7. Commingled G/PA6+2%wt Cloisite fibre-reinforced composite laminate.

Table 1. Glass fibre volume fraction estimation results (average) for G/PA6 and G/PA6+2%wt Cloisite.

Material/Method	ISO 3451	ASTM D2584
<i>G/PA6</i>	53.9%	53.7%
<i>G/PA6+2%wt Cloisite</i>	50.9%	51.2%

Fig.8. DMA equipment (top), 3-point bending fixture (bottom).

Fig.9. Typical optical micrographs of the microstructure in G/PA6 (top) and G/PA6+2%wt Cloisite (bottom) laminates from Batch 1 ($\times 10$). White circles indicate areas with voids.

Fig.10. Typical optical micrographs of the microstructure in G/PA6 (top) and G/PA6+2%wt Cloisite (bottom) laminates from Batch 1 ($\times 50$). White circle indicates areas with voids.

Fig.11. Typical optical micrographs of the microstructure in G/PA6 (top) and G/PA6+2%wt Cloisite (bottom) laminates from Batch 2 ($\times 10$).

Fig.12. Typical optical micrographs of the microstructure in G/PA6 (top) and G/PA6+2%wt Cloisite (bottom) laminates from Batch 2 ($\times 50$).

Fig.13. Representative storage modulus vs. temperature curves obtained by DMA for G/PA6 and G/PA6+2%wt Cloisite.

Fig.14. Representative $\tan \delta$ vs. temperature curves obtained by DMA for G/PA6 and G/PA6+2%wt Cloisite.

Fig.15. Representative heat release rate vs. time curves for PA6 and PA6+2%wt Cloisite as obtained by Cone Calorimetry at 50 kW/m^2 heat flux.

Table 2. Cone Calorimeter results for the two unreinforced material systems (PA6 and PA6+2%wt Cloisite) at 50 kW/m^2 heat flux.

Property/Material	PA6	PA6+2%wt Cloisite
$PHRR \text{ (kW/m}^2\text{)}$	1308.5 ± 40.3	740.3 ± 31.3
$THR \text{ (MJ/m}^2\text{)}$	222.3 ± 1.1	210.8 ± 1.0
$T_{ig} \text{ (s)}$	75 ± 2	70 ± 4
$TSR \text{ (m}^2\text{/m}^2\text{)}$	989.5 ± 44.9	1461.5 ± 31.7

Fig.16. Representative heat release rate vs. time curves for G/PA6 and G/PA6+2%wt Cloisite composites as obtained by Cone Calorimetry at 35 kW/m² heat flux.

Fig.17. Representative heat release rate vs. time curves for G/PA6 and G/PA6+2%wt Cloisite composites as obtained by Cone Calorimetry at 50 kW/m² heat flux.

Fig.18. Representative heat release rate vs. time curves for G/PA6 and G/PA6+2%wt Cloisite composites as obtained by Cone Calorimetry at 70 kW/m² heat flux.

Table 3. Cone Calorimeter results for the two reinforced material systems (PA6 and PA6+2%wt Cloisite-Batch 1) at 35 kW/m² heat flux.

Property/Material	G/PA6 (B1)	G/PA6+2%wt Cloisite (B1)
<i>PHRR (kW/m²)</i>	276.0 ± 21.7	236.7±19.3
<i>THR (MJ/m²)</i>	46.8±6.5	54.7±6.0
<i>T_{ig} (s)</i>	110±6	92±1
<i>TSR (m²/m²)</i>	169.0±67.3	241.3±68.0

Table 4. Cone Calorimeter results for the two reinforced material systems (PA6 and PA6+2%wt Cloisite-Batch 1) at 50 kW/m² heat flux.

Property/Material	G/PA6 (B2)	G/PA6+2%wt Cloisite (B2)
<i>PHRR (kW/m²)</i>	296.1 ± 11.2	272.6±17.8
<i>THR (MJ/m²)</i>	53.1±4.1	58.2±1.5
<i>T_{ig} (s)</i>	59±4.0	50.1±1.0
<i>TSR (m²/m²)</i>	268.4±59.0	307.3±13.3

Table 5. Cone Calorimeter results for the two reinforced material systems (PA6 and PA6+2%wt Cloisite-Batch 2) at 70 kW/m² heat flux.

Property/Material	G/PA6 (B2)	G/PA6+2%wt Cloisite (B2)
<i>PHRR (kW/m²)</i>	291.7±5.1	290.3±8.3
<i>THR (MJ/m²)</i>	50.8± 6.5	47.5± 0.7
<i>T_{ig} (s)</i>	30±2	29±1
<i>TSR (m²/m²)</i>	396.3±98.1	373.7±70.2

Table 6. UL-94 test results for the two unreinforced material systems (PA6 and PA6+2%wt Cloisite).

Property/Material	PA6	PA6+2%wt Cloisite
<i>T_i (s)</i>	256±177	35±13
<i>m_R (%)</i>	38±41	87±5

Table 7. UL-94 test results for the two commingled glass fibre-reinforced material systems (PA6 and PA6+2%wt Cloisite).

Property/Material	G/PA6	G/PA6+2%wt Cloisite
<i>T_i (s)</i>	227±20	117±32
<i>m_R (%)</i>	80±2	97±2